

TRIBUTE TO WANDA WESOLOWSKA ON HER 70th BIRTHDAY

In Zootaxa, Monograph 4899, a Festschrift issue in honour of Professor Wanda Wesolowska, was published in December 2020. This was on the occasion of her 70th birthday. The monograph was organized by Yuri Marusik, Charles Haddad, Galina Azarkina, Francesco Ballarin and Sarah Crews. Forty-one authors submitted seventeen papers dealing with spiders of several families.

Wanda is an internationally recognised expert in the taxonomy of jumping spiders, and was born in Włocławek (Central Poland) on 11 August 1950.

Wanda's academic research is mainly devoted to the taxonomy, faunistics and zoogeography of the Salticidae. The total number of her scientific works had reached 119 by November 2020. Her achievements in the study of jumping spiders are impressive indeed: 532 new species and 33 new genera described to date, and yet Wanda continues her studies. There is no other contemporary author who has described more new species and genera of Salticidae.

In the 1980s, when Wanda started working on salticids, the African fauna was still very poorly known. The plethora of modern salticid collections from Africa gave Wanda a unique opportunity to plunge into the intensive study of this large and diverse fauna. Here she worked with several people, such as Charles Haddad, Meg Cumming, Tony Russell-Smith and Galina Azarkina.

Of the 361 Salticidae species presently known from South Africa Wanda is the author or co-author of 180 of the species, which represents half of the South African fauna—exceptional!

Professor Wanda Wesolowska

For her contribution to African Arachnology, she was awarded the Lawrence Certificate of Merit in 2020 by the African Arachnological Society during the 13th Colloquium of the African Arachnological Society at Klein Klariba.

At last a name for this beautiful spider - see next page 2

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FESTSCHRIFT IN HONOUR OF WANDA WESOŁOWSKA ON THE OCCASION OF HER 70TH BIRTHDAY

Y.M. MARUSIK, C.R. HADDAD, G.N. AZARKINA, F. BALLARIN & S.C. CREWS (EDS.)

In four papers published in the Festschrift, several new genera and species of South African spiders were described.

I. AZARKINA, G.N. & HADDAD, C.R. 2020. Partial revision of the Afrotropical Ballini, with the description of seven new genera (Araneae: Salticidae). *Zootaxa* 4899: 15-92.

In this paper by Azarkina and Haddad (2020), they partly revised the Afrotropical Ballini Salticidae. The Ballini is peculiar for the evolution of a variety of mimetic body forms that have evolved in such a small group, including proposed ant- or pseudoscorpion-mimicking and beetle-mimicking species.

The aims of the paper was 1) to establish new genera of Afrotropical Ballini; (2) to describe new species; (3) to provide new combinations. The following results affect the South African fauna.

NEW GENERA

1. *Oviballus* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020

The genus is monotypic. The generic name refers to a superficial resemblance to sheep, and is derived from the Latin noun "ovis", meaning "sheep", and the name of the salticid genus *Ballus*.

Oviballus vidae Azarkina & Haddad, 2020 (Photos: V. van der Walt)

2. *Planamarengo* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020

The genus is known from three species, with *Planamarengo bimaculata* (Peckham & Peckham, 1903) known from South Africa. A canopy-dwelling and arboreal genus, occasionally recorded from grasslands, savanna and thickets.

Planamarengo bimaculata (Peckham & Peckham, 1903) (Photos: V. van der Walt)

3. *Propiomarengo* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020

The genus is known from two species with *P. foordi* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020 and *P. plana* (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013) known from South Africa. Tibiae I with long dense ventral setae in both sexes. Arboreal genus associated with shrubs.

4. *Tenuiballus* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020

Known from males of two new species, *T. coronatus* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020 and *T. minor* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020. This genus was collected from grassy savannas.

Male of *Tenuiballus coronatus* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020 (Photos: V. van der Walt)

5. *Wandawe* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020

Wandawe consists of three species known from both sexes. It includes *W. australe* ♂♀, from South Africa), *W. benjamini* (♂♀, from South Africa) and *W. tigrina* (♂♀, from Kenya). They have been collected as arboreal species collected in forest and savanna habitats.

Female of *Wandawe australe* (Photos: V. van der Walt)

Festschrift in honour of Wanda Wesolowska (*continued*)

II. JOCQUÉ, R. & HENRARD, A. 2020. Three new species of the genus *Ranops* (Araneae: Zodariidae) from southern Africa. *Zootaxa* 4899: 186-200.

The genus *Ranops* Jocqué, 1991 was previously only known from three species. Three new species of the genus were described here, all from both sexes: *R. robiniae* Jocqué & Henrard, 2020 from South Africa, *R. thari-nae* Jocqué & Henrard, 2020 from Botswana, and *R. wandae* Jocqué & Henrard, 2020 from Namibia.

Ranops has long legs, up to three times the total length of the spider, and the leg formula 4321, is unique in the Zodariinae. Even in the living animal, this important feature is obvious. Further remarkable characters are the wide sternum, which it shares only with some *Systemoplacis* Simon, 1907 and *Capheris* Simon, 1898 (but these belong in another subfamily), the dense covering of the entire body with shiny, flattened incised setae, and the peculiar dorsal abdominal pattern with pairs of pale spots.

Ranops robiniae was sampled from pitfall traps during SANSa surveys in the Gauteng, Limpopo, Mpumalanga and Free State Provinces in South Africa.

Ranops robiniae from Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve in South Africa (Photos: N. Josling)

Ranops robiniae habitus A. male B. Female C. female ventral view

III. OMELKO, M.M., MARUSIK, Y.M. & LYLE, R. 2020. A survey of *Diphya* Nicolet, 1849 (Araneae: Tetragnathidae) from South Africa. *Zootaxa* 4899: 259-279.

In this paper, five species of *Diphya* Nicolet, 1849 are recognized in the fauna of South Africa. Four of these species are new: *D. foordi* (♂♀), *D. leroyorum* (♂), *D. vanderwaltae* (♀) and *D. wesolowskiae* (♂♀). The male of *D. simoni* Kauri, 1950 is described for the first time. *Diphya tanikawai* Marusik, 2017 was found to be a junior synonym of *D. simoni*.

Diphya is an average-sized genus of spiders belonging to its own tribe, Diphyaeni of the family Tetragnathidae. So far, 15 named species are known in the Neotropical and Afrotropical Realms, as well as in the southeastern Palearctic (central and northeast China, Korea, Japan, and in the Maritime Province of Russia) (World Spider Catalog 2020).

Diphya sp.

Eye pattern

Festschrift in honour of Wanda Wesolowska (continued)

A survey of *Diphya* (continued)

Distribution. *Diphya simoni* has the widest range and known from the Cape Peninsula in the southwest to the Kruger National Park in the northeast, followed by *D. foordi* with the second widest range. *Diphya wesolowskiae* is restricted to the eastern part of the country and two remaining species are known from single localities.

Behaviour. Most of the specimens were collected during SANSA surveys. They have been sampled with all the collecting methods, ranging from sweeping, beating, pitfall traps, litter sifting and vacuum sampling. They have been recorded from the Forest, Grassland, Savanna, Fynbos and Indian Coastal Belt forests.

III. DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & FOORD, S.H. 2020. Revision of the Afrotropical crab-spider genus *Parabomis* Kulczyński, 1901 (Araneae: Thomisidae). *Zootaxa* 4899: 161-174.

The Afrotropical spider genus *Parabomis* Kulczyński, 1901 was revised. Members of *Parabomis* are some of the smallest thomisids known, and occur from Eritrea in the north of Africa to South Africa in the south, but are absent from Madagascar. Prior to this study, three species were known, namely *P. levanderi* Kulczyński, 1901 (Eritrea, ♂), *P. martini* Lessert, 1919 (Tanzania, ♂♀) and *P. anabensis* Lawrence, 1928 (Namibia, ♀). Four new species are described: *P. elsae* from South Africa (♂♀), *P. megae* from Zimbabwe and South Africa (♂♀), *P. pilosus* from Botswana and South Africa (♂♀) and *P. wandae* from Ghana (♂♀). Read more about *Parabomis* spp. on page 25 of this newsletter.

Female and male *Parabomis megae* Photo J. Whitaker

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

OTHER PUBLICATIONS

WESOŁOWSKA, W., AZARKINA, G.N. & WIŚNIEWSKI, K. 2020. A revision of *Pachyballus* Simon, 1900 and *Peplometus* Simon, 1900 (Araneae, Salticidae, Ballini) with descriptions of new species. *ZooKeys* 944: 47-98.

Two genera from the tribe Ballini (Araneae, Salticidae), *Pachyballus* Simon, 1900 and *Peplometus* Simon, 1900, are remarkable for their resemblance to beetles. *Pachyballus* and *Peplometus* are closely related and share most morphological characters. They are small but robust spiders, with a strongly flattened body that is covered with a very hard, sclerotised integument. The dorsum of their body has a characteristic pitted microsculpture.

Thirteen species were included in the taxonomic revision of the two genera by Wesolowska *et al.* (2020). Six of them are new to science. The species are known from South Africa are:

- *Pachyballus miniscutulus* (♂♀, South Africa),
- *Pachyballus castaneus* Simon, 1900 (♂♀, South Africa)
- *Pachyballus flavipes* Simon, 1909 (♂♀, Ivory Coast, Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea, D.R. Congo, Uganda, Kenya, Tanzania, Angola, Botswana, Zimbabwe, South Africa)
- *Pachyballus transversus* Simon, 1900 (♂♀, Ethiopia, Somalia, Guinea-Bissau, Cameroon, Congo, D.R. Congo, Tanzania, Mozambique, South Africa)
- *Peplometus chlorophthalmus* Simon, 1900 (♂♀, D.R. Congo, South Africa)

Pachyballus sp. (Photo: P. Webb)

Peplometus chlorophthalmus

Pachyballus flavipes

PEKÁR, S., PETRAKOVA DUŠÁTKOVÁ, L., MICHÁLEK, O. & HADDAD, C.R. 2020. Coexistence of two termite-eating specialists (Araneae). *Ecological Entomology* 45: 1307-1317.

In this study, various niche dimensions, namely temporal, spatial and trophic, of *Stenaelurillus guttiger* and *S. modestus* from South Africa, were investigated, to find whether these two species co-exist and along which niche dimension(s) they differentiate. The two species co-occurred in two out of five study sites in the Ndumo Game Reserve. Body size was not significantly different between the species. The phenology was shifted so that one species matured earlier.

Circadian activity was not different, as both species were diurnal and active at similar times. Both species preyed almost exclusively on termites. The fundamental trophic niche was very similar and rather narrow. The realised trophic niche at the prey order level of both species was similar, but at the genus level it was different. In *S. modestus* it was narrower, as it captured mainly *Odontotermes*, while *S. guttiger* exploited a few termite species. The size of prey captured was also similar between the two species. The frequency of intraguild predation was negligible. They concluded that both *Stenaelurillus* species are specialised termitophagous predators. The two species can coexist across broad spatial scales due to spatial segregation on the landscape.

Stenaelurillus guttiger (Photo: P. Webb)

South African National Parks: Spider diversity and conservation

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman

South African National Parks (SANParks) was formed in 1926, and currently manages 22 parks consisting of 3,751,113 hectares, over 3% of the total area of South Africa. In terms of the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act, 2003 (Act No 57 of 2003), the primary mandate of SANParks is to oversee the conservation of South Africa's biodiversity, landscapes and associated heritage assets through a system of national parks. In 1997, the ARC registered a project (**DIPSA 1296**) at SANParks to determine the diversity of arachnids in the different parks. Firstly, all available data on specimens described from the parks was collated into a database. Surveys were then initiated with the overall aim to collect, identify, describe and make an inventory of the Arachnida species; to determine the number of species already protected in each park; to eventually publish a checklist for each park; to identify the species of special concern; and indicate possible exotic species. The information generated through these surveys feeds into the SANSa conservation assessments used to compile the Red Data List of the spiders of South Africa. The project ended in December 2018 and the final spider reports with metadata has been prepared for the SANParks database. Through the DIPSA 1296 project, 13 of the 22 national parks were surveyed and a total of 2360 species have been recorded.

PARK	FAMILY	GENERA	SPECIES
ADDO	47	184	276
AUGRABIES	29	85	109
BONTEBOK	44	134	184
GARDEN ROUTE	50	182	278
GOLDEN GATE	36	108	155
KGALAGADI	14	32	33
KAROO	39	103	133
KRUGER	47	233	417
MARAKELE	35	99	134
MOUNTAIN ZEBRA	39	109	151
NAMAQUA	29	77	103
RICHTERSVELD	29	69	89
TABLE MOUNTAIN	47	179	298

The final reports for three of the parks have been completed: the Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2020); Marakele National Park (see pages 7-15 of this issue) and Augrabies National Park (16-24).

BIOSPHERE RESERVES

UNESCO's Man and the Biosphere programme addresses the impact of man on the environment by studying the social, ecological and economic implications of biodiversity loss. It then takes steps to minimise this loss through sharing of knowledge, research and monitoring, education and training, and multilateral decision-making. Biosphere reserves are nominated by their governments for inclusion to the Man and the Biosphere programme. Whether they are terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine in nature, all are experimental areas where different approaches to integrated environmental management are tested. This is important, as it helps to deepen our knowledge of what works in conservation and sustainable development. South Africa's six biosphere sites are:

- Kogelberg,
- Cape Winelands,
- Cape West Coast Reserve,
- Waterberg,
- Kruger to Canyons Reserve,
- Vhembe.

SANSa have extensively sampled in several of these Biosphere Reserves. Presently we are preparing checklists of spiders found in these reserves, with information on species distribution, guild occupation, endemism, and species of special concern.

The Waterberg Biosphere was the first reserve that we have prepared a species list for. SANSa has been involved in several surveys in the Waterberg, resulting in:

- total of 3887 records, sampled from
- 50 localities in the Waterberg
- representing 501 spider species
- from 49 families

A final list will eventually be published. Presently, information on the spiders of the Waterberg can be viewed at <http://www.waterberg-bioquest.co.za/>

A checklist of the spiders can be downloaded, and on display are photographs that are available for some of the species. This is an interesting website to visit and learn more about the fauna and flora of the Waterberg Biosphere Reserve.

You can contact Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman if you want to share more photographs at DippenaarA@arc.agric.za.

HOME IN A SHELL

Anka Eichhoff, spider enthusiast from Namibia

Nearly everywhere in the veld in Namibia you can see little white shells (about 12 mm in length) lying on the ground. They are the empty houses of *Xerocerastus* land snails.

I was greatly surprised when I saw these little snail houses hanging from a grass stalk, each about 10 to 15 cm above the ground level. On top of one of the snail houses sat a little black and white jumping spider. When I came nearer she vanished into the shell and looked at me. When I moved even nearer, it drew a silk curtain to close the entrance. Some of the shells are fixed to the plant material with the entrance to the top, others' entrances point down or even to a side.

So I took home some of these shell-homes for further investigation and even broke one open to see what's inside. Half of the shell forms the egg chamber and the half with the entrance is the retreat of the mother spider.

Shell showing the different areas occupied by the spider

They are members of the Salticidae probably either *Pellenes epularis* or *Pellenes geniculatus*, but the species are difficult to separate without examining preserved specimens.

Empty shell with the spider

RECENT PUBLICATIONS

- AZARKINA, G.N. & HADDAD, C.R.** 2020. Partial revision of the Afrotropical Ballini, with the description of seven new genera (Araneae: Salticidae). *Zootaxa* 4899: 15–92.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & FOORD, S.H.** 2020. Revision of the Afrotropical crab-spider genus *Parabomis* Kulczyński, 1901 (Araneae: Thomisidae). *Zootaxa* 4899: 161–174.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & FOORD, S.H.** 2020. First record of the orb-web spider *Araneus holzapfelae* Lessert, 1936 from South Africa (Arachnida: Araneidae). *SANSA News* 35: 19–21.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., FOORD, S.H. & HADDAD, C.R.** 2020. Notes on the orb-web spider *Araneus apricus* (Karsch, 1884) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA News* 36: 12–14.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., WEBB, P., FOORD, S.H. & HADDAD, C.R.** 2020. New locality data for the orb-web spider *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA News* 36: 15–16.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H. & LOTZ, L.N.** 2020. *The Oxyopidae of South Africa*, version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, 57 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H., LOTZ, L.N. & BIRD, T.L.** 2020. *The Ammoxenidae of South Africa*, version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, 20 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H. & LOTZ, L.N.** 2020. *The Caponiidae of South Africa*, version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, 24 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H. & LOTZ, L.N.** 2020. *The Hersiliidae of South Africa*, version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, 23 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H. & LOTZ, L.N.** 2020. *The Deinopidae of South Africa*, version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, 16 pp.
- JOCQUÉ, R. & HENRARD, A.** 2020. Three new species of the genus *Ranops* (Araneae: Zodariidae) from southern Africa. *Zootaxa* 4899: 186–200.
- KALLAL, R.J. & HORMIGA, G.** 2020. Phylogenetic placement of the stone-nest orb-weaving spider *Nemoscolus* Simon, 1895 (Araneae: Araneidae) and the description of the first species from Australia. *Invertebrate Systematics*, 34: 893–905.
- MITCHELL, S., SOLE, C. & LYLE, R.** 2020. Teratological cases of the ocular patterns in the South African endemic trapdoor spider genus *Stasimopus* Simon (1892) (Araneae, Mygalomorphae, Stasimopidae). *African Zoology* 55: 363–367
- OMELKO, M.M., MARUSIK, Y.M. & LYLE, R.** 2020. A survey of *Diphya* Nicolet, 1849 (Araneae: Tetragnathidae) from South Africa. *Zootaxa* 4899: 259–279.
- PEKÁR, S., DUŠÁTKOVÁ, L.P., MICHÁLEK, O. & HADDAD, C.R.** 2020. Coexistence of two termite-eating specialists (Araneae). *Ecological Entomology* 45: 1307–1317.
- PONOMAREV, A. V. & SHMATKO, V. Y.** 2020. A review of spiders of the genera *Trachyzeloes* [sic] Lohmander, 1944 and *Marinarozelotes Ponomarev*, gen. n. (Aranei: Gnaphosidae) from the southeast of the Russian Plain and the Caucasus. *Caucasian Entomological Bulletin* 16(1): 125–139.
- RODRIGUES, B.V.B. & RHEIMS, C.A.** 2020. Phylogenetic analysis of the subfamily Prodidominae (Arachnida: Araneae: Gnaphosidae). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 190: 654–708.
- SHIVAMBU, T.C., SHIVAMBU, N., LYLE, R., JACOBS, A., KUMSCHICK, S., FOORD, S.H. & ROBERTSON, M.P.** 2020. Tarantulas (Araneae: Theraphosidae) in the pet trade in South Africa. *African Zoology* 55: 323–336.
- ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ, F., NGUYEN, P., SADÍLEK, D., ŠTUNDLOVÁ, J., JUST, P., HADDAD, C.R., KOÇ, H., RANAWANA, K.B., STOCKMANN, M., YAGMUR, E.A. & KOVAŘÍK, F.** 2020. Evolutionary dynamics of rDNA clusters on chromosomes of buthid scorpions (Chelicerata: Arachnida). *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 131: 547–565.
- WESOŁOWSKA, W., AZARKINA, G.N. & WIŚNIEWSKI, K.** 2020. A revision of *Pachyballus* Simon, 1900 and *Peplometus* Simon, 1900 (Araneae, Salticidae, Ballini) with descriptions of new species. *ZooKeys* 944: 47–98.
- WIŚNIEWSKI, K.** 2020. Over 40 years with jumping spiders: on the 70th birthday of Wanda Wesolowska. *Zootaxa* 4899: 5–15.

A list of spider species found in the Marakele National Park, Limpopo Province, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT

This article provides the first checklist of the spider fauna of the Marakele National Park, including their conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution. Standard collecting methods were used to sample spiders during a survey in February 2010. Thirty-six families that include 100 genera and 135 species were recorded. Salticidae (19 spp.), Araneidae (18 spp.) and Thomisidae (17 spp.) were the most species-rich families, while 14 families were only represented by a single species. About 6 % of the South African spider fauna and 14 % of the Limpopo Province fauna are protected in the park; 21 species are South African endemics, but only one (*Cheiracanthium foordi* Lotz, 2015) is a Marakele National Park endemic.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

In terms of the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act, 2003 (Act No 57 of 2003), the primary mandate of SANParks is to oversee the conservation of South Africa's biodiversity, landscapes and associated heritage assets through a system of national parks. In 1997 the Agricultural Research Council registered a project (DIPSA 1296) at SANParks, with the aim of determining the diversity of arachnids in the different parks.

McGeoch *et al.* (2011) recently identified five major invertebrate groups that can serve as surrogates in conservation planning and monitoring in South Africa, namely Araneae, Scarabaeidae (Coleoptera), Lepidoptera, Odonata and Formicidae (Hymenoptera).

One of the core research areas of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) is to determine the number of arachnid species presently conserved in protected areas. The South African National Parks (SANParks) are key to South Africa's conservation initiatives (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2006; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016). Species distribution data generated through SANParks and other surveys feed into the conservation assessments used to compile the Red Data List of the Arachnida of South Africa (Lyle & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015).

We report on a survey in the Marakele National Park (MNP), on the south-western border of the Limpopo province. The study aimed to determine spider diversity and generate baseline data, such as the conservation status and level of endemism of each species sampled, which can serve as a reference for future studies in the MNP.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: The MNP is situated in the Waterberg region, near the town of Thabazimbi in the Limpopo Province, South Africa (Fig. 1). It is a core conservation area in the Waterberg Biosphere Reserve and includes the highest point in the Limpopo Province (2110 m a.s.l.). It receives between 500–750 mm of rainfall annually, and includes three vegetation types (Fig. 2), namely Western Sandy Bushveld, Waterberg Mountain Bushveld and Waterberg/Magaliesberg Summit Sourveld (Schoeman & Foord

Collecting methods: Sampling followed the standardised SANSa protocol, as described by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2015). This included sweep-net sampling, beating, leaf litter sifting, pitfall trapping, and active searches during the day and night. This study forms part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) and took place in February 2010.

Voucher specimens: Specimens were predominantly deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC—Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria. Taxonomic constraints and undescribed species necessitated the use of morphospecies in some instances.

Endemism value (END): This value was determined based on the known distribution of each species: (6) only known from the type locality; (5) endemic to the Limpopo Province (LE); (4) known from Limpopo and an adjoining province; (3) endemic to South Africa (SAE); (2) endemic to southern Africa (STHE); (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region (AE); (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region (C).

Conservation status (CS): This value was determined for each species from a recent Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa. LC: least concern, when species has a wide distribution; DD: data deficient, through either a lack of distribution data or taxonomic resources; NE: not evaluated; VU: vulnerable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: In total, 135 species in 100 genera and 36 families were recorded (Table 1; Appendix 1). Three species were not evaluated, due to the lack of resolved taxonomy of their genera (Table 2; Appendix 1). Although the survey was conducted over a very short period, the number of species collected compares well with other Limpopo surveys, e.g. the Nylsvley Nature Reserve, where 175 species were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2009).

FIGURE 1: Map of the vegetation types in the Marakele National Park. Sampling locations: M1–M4.

FIGURE 2: Vegetation types in the Marakele National Park: (A) mountain bushveld and (b) summit vegetation.

Family diversity: Of the 36 spider families collected from MNP (Table 1; Appendix 1), the Salticidae (19 spp.), Araneidae (18 spp.) and Thomisidae (17 spp.) were the most species-rich, while 14 families were only represented by a single species. Similar patterns were found in other surveys, such as the Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.* 2009), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2009) and Makelali Nature Reserve (Whitmore *et al.* 2001).

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Marakele National Park, with the total number of families, genera (gen) and species sampled.

FAMILY	gen.	spp.	FAMILY	gen.	spp.
Agelenidae	2	2	Lycosidae	7	9
Ammoxenidae	1	1	Oxyopidae	3	8
Araneidae	13	18	Palpimanidae	1	1
Cheiracanthiidae	1	2	Philodromidae	4	5
Clubionidae	1	1	Pholcidae	1	2
Corinnidae	2	2	Pisauridae	2	2
Ctenidae	1	1	Salticidae	11	19
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Deinopidae	1	1	Selenopidae	2	3
Dictynidae	2	2	Sicariidae	1	1
Entypesidae	1	1	Sparassidae	2	2
Eresidae	1	1	Tetragnathidae	2	2
Gnaphosidae	4	4	Theraphosidae	4	4
Hahniidae	1	1	Theridiidae	7	9
Hersiliidae	1	2	Thomisidae	10	17
Idiopidae	1	1	Trachelidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	1	1	Uloboridae	2	2
Liocranidae	1	1	Zodariidae	3	4

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the Marakele National Park.

DISTRIBUTION	spp.	%
CONSERVATION STATUS		
Data deficient (DD)	2	1.5
Not evaluated (NE)	3	2.2
Least concern (LC)	130	96.3
Vulnerable (VU)	0	0
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	14	11.0
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	62	45.6
2 – Southern Africa endemics (STHE)	34	25.0
3 – South Africa endemics (SAE)	22	14.7
4 – South Africa endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	0	0.7
5 – Limpopo endemics (LE)	0	0.7
6 – Marakele National Park (MNP)	1	0.7
Not evaluated	3	2.2

Species endemism: Of the 135 species sampled, only two species, *Cheiracanthium foordi* Lotz, 2015 (Cheiracanthiidae) and *Rastellus florisbad* Platnick & Griffin, 1990 (Ammoxenidae) are data deficient (DD). The former is the only Limpopo and Marakele endemic sampled. Only one female specimen is presently known. Three species of the families Dictynidae, Theridiidae

and Corinnidae were not evaluated (NE), due to the taxonomic resolution of the respective genera (Table 2; Appendix 1). Fourteen species have a wide distribution and were possibly introduced to Africa. This includes several cosmopolitan species, such as the Araneidae species *Cyclosa insulana* (Costa, 1834) and *Cyrtophora citricola* (Forsskål 1775), *Archaeodictyna conducta* (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876) (Dictynidae), *Selenops radiatus* Latreille, 1819 (Selenopidae) and *Uloborus plumipes* Lucas, 1846 (Uloboridae). Sixty-two species are African endemics, 34 are southern African endemics, and 22 South African endemics.

CONCLUSION

Although five surveys have been published on spiders of the National Parks, this is only the second paper that contains final survey results after the SANParks project ended in 2019, following the recently published results of the Addo Elephant National Park. These inventories will not only make a significant contribution to the existing knowledge of arthropod biodiversity in South Africa's protected areas, but will also facilitate movement towards full-scale use of invertebrates in monitoring and other conservation activities.

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REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR, S., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., MODIBA, M.A. & KHOZA, T.T. 2008. A checklist of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Polokwane Nature Reserve, Limpopo Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50: 10–17.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2016. SANSa: Protected areas: National Parks. *SANSa News* 25: 5–6.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & HADDAD, C.R. 2006. What is the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) all about? *SANSa News* 1: 1–3.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H., LYLE, R., LOTZ, L.N. & MARAIS, P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245–277.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., VAN DEN BERG, A. & PRENDINI, L. 2009. Spiders and Scorpions

(Arachnida: Araneae, Scorpiones) of the Nylsvley Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 51(#161): 1–9.

LYLE, R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2015. Red listing of South African spiders. *SANSa Newsletter* 23: 1.

MCGEOCH, M.A., SITHOLE, H., SAMWAYS, M.J., SIMAIKA, J.P., PRYKE, J.S., PICKER, M., YUS, C., ARMSTRONG, A.J., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., ENGELBRECHT, I.A., BRASCHLER, B. & HAMER, M. 2011. Conservation and monitoring of invertebrates in terrestrial protected areas. *Koedoe* 53(#1000): 1–13.

SCHOEMAN, C.S. & FOORD, S.H. 2012. A checklist of epigaeic ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from the Marakele National Park, Limpopo, South Africa. *Koedoe* 54 (#1030): 1–7.

WHITMORE, C., SLOTOW, R., CROUCH, T.E. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2001. Checklist of spiders (Araneae) from a savanna ecosystem, Northern Province, South Africa: including a new family record. *Durban Museum Novitates* 26: 10–19.

FIGURE 3: Two species from the Marakele National Park: (A) *Mexcala elegans* Peckham & Peckham, 1903 (Salticidae); (B) *Nilus margaritatus* (Pocock, 1898) (Pisauridae). Photos: P. Webb.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of the Marakele National Park, listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CS) and global distribution.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST	
AGELENIDAE	<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	
AMMOXENIDAE	<i>Rastellus florisbad</i> Platnick & Griffin, 1990	3	DD	SAE	
ARANEIDAE	<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Nemoscolus cotti</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1885)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Pararaneus spectator</i> (Karsch, 1885)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	
	CHEIRACANTHIDAE	<i>Cheiracanthium foordi</i> Lotz, 2015	6	DD	MNP
		<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
CLUBIONIDAE	<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE	
CORINNIDAE	<i>Cambalida dippenaarae</i> Haddad, 2012	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Castianeira</i> sp.		NE		
CTENIDAE	<i>Ctenus gulosus</i> Des Arts, 1912	2	LC	STHE	
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE	<i>Ancylotrypa brevipalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE	
DEINOPIIDAE	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	
DICTYNIDAE	<i>Archaeodictyna conducta</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.		NE		
ENTYPESIDAE	<i>Hermacha mazoena</i> Hewitt, 1915	2	LC	STHE	
ERESIDAE	<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE	
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Asemesthes paynteri</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	
HAHNIIDAE	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE	
HERSILIIDAE	<i>Hersilia arborea</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE	

APPENDIX 1: continued.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST	
IDIOPIDAE	<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE	
LINYPHIIDAE	<i>Tybaertiella krugeri</i> (Simon, 1894)	1	LC	AE	
LIOCRANIDAE	<i>Rhaeboctesis transvaalensis</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE	
LYCOSIDAE	<i>Allocosa lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Allocosa montana</i> Roewer, 1959	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Pardosa injucunda</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE	
	OXYOPIDAE	<i>Hamataliwa fronticornis</i> (Lessert, 1927)	1	LC	AE
		<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hamataliwa rufocaligata</i> Simon, 1898		1	LC	AE	
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915		1	LC	AE	
<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)		1	LC	AE	
<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915		1	LC	AE	
<i>Peucetia crucifera</i> Lawrence, 1927		2	LC	STHE	
<i>Peucetia lucasi</i> (Vinson, 1863)		1	LC	AE	
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	
PHILODROMIDAE	<i>Hirriusa variegata</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	
	PHOLCIDAE	<i>Smeringopus badplaas</i> Huber, 2012	4	LC	SAE
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947		2	LC	STHE	
PISAUROIDAE	<i>Euprosthops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Nilus margaritatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	
SALTICIDAE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Dendryphantès hararensis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Evarcha ignea</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus deamatus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus demonstrativus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus lesserti</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus orchestra</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE	

APPENDIX 1: continued.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST
	<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hyllus treleaveni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Mexcala elegans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Plexippus tsholotsho</i> Wesolowska, 2011	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Stenaelurillus guttiger</i> (Simon, 1901)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tusitala hirsuta</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes maritima</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
SELENOPIIDAE	<i>Anyphops fitzsimoni</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops tuckeri</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Selenops radiatus</i> Latreille, 1819	0	LC	C
SICARIIDAE	<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Eusparassus jaegeri</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	1	LC	AE
TETRAGNATHIDAE	<i>Leucauge levanderi</i> (Kulczynski, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C
THERAPHOSIDAE	<i>Brachionopus pretoriae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ceratogyrus darlingi</i> Pocock, 1897	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Harpactirella overdijki</i> Gallon, 2010	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Idiothele nigrofulva</i> (Pocock, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Argyrodes zonatus</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Phoroncidia eburnea</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion piliphilum</i> Strand, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Theridion</i> sp. 3		NE	
THOMISIDAE	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1941	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> Lucas, 1864	0	LC	C
	<i>Parabomis martini</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
	<i>Runcinia insecta</i> (L. Koch, 1875)	0	LC	C

APPENDIX 1: continued.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST
	<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Synema imitator</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisops pupa</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus granulatus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Xysticus mulleri</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
TRACHELIDAE	<i>Afrocecto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
ULOBORIDAE	<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Diores magicus</i> Jocqué & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1992	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Diores recurvatus</i> Jocqué, 1990	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE

Endemicity (END): (6) only known from the type locality, Marakele National Park endemic; (5) endemic to Limpopo Province; (4) known from two adjoining provinces; (3) endemic to South Africa; (2) endemic to southern Africa; (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region; (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status (CS): LC, least concern; DD, data deficient; NE, not evaluated; VU, vulnerable.

Distribution (DIS): C, cosmopolitan or wider than Africa; AE, African endemic; STHE, southern African endemic; SAE, South African endemic; LE, Limpopo endemic.

A checklist of the spiders of the Augrabies National Park in the Northern Cape Province, South Africa (Arachnida, Araneae)

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides the first annotated species list of the spiders presently known and protected in the Augrabies National Park. A total of 109 species from 29 families are presently protected in the park. The most species-rich families are the Salticidae (17 spp.), Gnaphosidae (17 spp.) and Thomisidae (8 spp.), while 9 families are represented by singletons. Their conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution is provided. Approximately 4.9 % of the total South African spider fauna is protected in the Augrabies National Park; 37 of the species recorded are South African endemics, 7 species are Northern Cape endemics, and one species, *Hexophthalma leroyi* Lotz, 2018, is endemic to the park.

Keywords: South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), biodiversity, conservation

INTRODUCTION

The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) was initiated in 1997 with the main aim to document the diversity and distribution of arachnids in the country. Surveys are carried out across the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015), thereby generating data that are needed for conservation assessment of species.

South Africa's spider species are not evenly distributed across the country, and the highest diversity has been recorded in the provinces of Limpopo and KwaZulu-Natal (Foord *et al.* 2011). Little is still known of the spiders of the Northern Cape. The first survey of this area was undertaken by Leonhard Schultze, with Purcell (1908) and Simon (1910) describing many new species from South Africa, Namibia and Botswana based on those samples (Haddad & Marusik 2019). The only other Northern Cape surveys were from pistachio orchards (Haddad *et al.* 2004, 2005; Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006), Nama Karoo grassland (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2005), and the spiders of the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2018).

This paper presents the first information on the spider fauna of the Augrabies National Park in the Northern Cape. Information on endemism and conservation status for 108 species are provided.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: The Augrabies National Park (ANP), is located 120 km west of Upington in the Northern Cape Province an area of 820 km² (Fig. 1). The ANP was proclaimed in 1966 and is situated on both sides of the Orange River between 28°25'S-28°38'S latitude and 20°15'E-20°20'E longitude. The park is a semi-desert arid rocky area and the Orange River flows through the rocky topography (Fig. 2).

It is the largest conservation area within the Orange River Nama Karoo biome. The rainfall, mainly during the summer, is erratic and can be as high as 391 mm per year but as low as 40 mm per year. The winters are cold, as low as -2.9°C (June and July), with maximum temperatures highest in summer (December, January and February), at 42.9°C.

Sampling methods and identification: Sampling of invertebrates especially in arid regions are time consuming and difficult. Specimens were mainly sampled *ad hoc* by visiting scientists, as well as sampling by the fourth author, who was employed in the ANP for a short period. He sampled specimens by hand and preserved them in 70% ethanol. Identifications were done in Pretoria and voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria. Specimens housed in the NCA and documented on the SANSa database were used to compile the first checklist of the spiders of ANP (Appendix 1). Some of the species could not be identified to species level because only immature specimens were sampled or the taxonomy of the family is still unresolved.

Endemism value: The endemism value was provided for each species (Appendix 1) based on its currently known distribution. Seven endemism categories are recognized: 6 = ANPE, known only from type locality (Augrabies National Park Endemic); 5 = NCE, known only from the Northern Cape Province, but wider than the type locality; 4 = SAE known from two adjoining provinces (South African Endemic); 3 = South Africa, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining (SAE); 2 = STHE, known from southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers); 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African Endemic); 0 = known from Africa and wider (C).

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider project, the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures or those represented by new or undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or only known from very old material, were listed as DDT (data deficient for taxonomic reasons), or DD, when the species could not be identified. Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of Least Concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC. Species of special concern usually belong to category 5 or 6.

FIGURE 1: Map showing the site of the Augrabies National Park.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Family diversity: A total of 108 species from 85 genera and 30 families have been recorded from the ANP to date (Table 1; Appendix 1). The only known records of spiders from the ANP was the 26 spp. listed in the First Atlas of South African Spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010) and two species that were recently newly recorded from the park, *Diploglena arida* Haddad, 2015 (Haddad 2015) and *Hexophthalma leroyi* Lotz, 2018 (Lotz 2018). Some of the common species sampled are shown in Figs 3A-L.

In this study, the Salticidae (17 spp.), Gnaphosidae (17 spp.) and Thomisidae (8 spp.) were the most species-rich families (Table 1). It compares well with the survey of the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve, where 32 families represented by 108 genera and 136 species were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2018), and where the Salticidae, Thomisidae and Gnaphosidae were the most species-rich families. The Tswalu Kalahari Reserve falls within the Savanna Biome and the vegetation is more diverse than in ANP, and this contribute to the higher diversity there. However, as sampling was carried out ad hoc and not quantitatively, these results may not be a true reflection of the actual spider richness.

Salticidae: The Salticidae are free-living spiders found on vegetation and the soil surface. All of the seventeen species are new records for the park. Only three of the species are endemic to South Africa, while eight are southern African endemics and three African endemics. No species is endemic to the Northern Cape, but two species are possible new to science. *Hasarius adansoni* (Audouin, 1826) is the only cosmopolitan species sampled.

Gnaphosidae: The Gnaphosidae are free-living spiders found mainly on the soil surface. Members of this family are known to be more abundant in drier regions. Five species, *Asemesthes numisma* Tucker, 1923, *Austrodomus scaber* (Purcell, 1904), *Theuma maculata* Purcell, 1907, *Xerophaeus hottentottus* Purcell, 1908 and *Zelotes lavus* Tucker, 1923 were previously reported from the park. Five species are endemic to South Africa, while six are southern African endemics. Only one has a wide African distribution. No gnaphosid species recorded is endemic in the Northern Cape, but two species are possibly new to science.

FIGURE 2: Habitat types in the Augrabies National Park. Photos: E. le Roux

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of Augrabies National Park, with total number of families, genera (G) and species (S) sampled.

FAMILY	G	S	FAMILY	G	S
Agelenidae	2	2	Pholcidae	2	2
Ammoxenidae	1	2	Phyxelididae	1	1
Araneidae	3	4	Salticidae	15	17
Caponiidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Cheiracanthiidae	2	2	Segestriidae	1	1
Clubionidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	3
Dictynidae	1	1	Sicariidae	2	2
Eresidae	3	5	Sparassidae	3	4
Gnaphosidae	11	17	Theraphosidae	2	2
Hersiliidae	2	3	Theridiidae	6	7
Lycosidae	3	3	Thomisidae	6	8
Oecobiidae	2	2	Trachelidae	1	1
Oxyopidae	2	4	Uloboridae	1	1
Palpimanidae	2	3	Zodariidae	4	5
Philodromidae	3	4			

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the Augrabies National Park.

DISTRIBUTION	SPP	%
CONSERVATION STATUS		
Data deficient (DD)	7	6.4
Not evaluated (NE)	7	6.4
Least concern	93	85.3
Rare	1	0.9
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	7	6.4
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	23	21.1
2 – Southern Africa endemics (STHE)	38	34.9
3 – South Africa endemics (SAE)	14	12.8
4 – South Africa endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	8	7.3
5 – Northern Cape endemics (LE)	7	6.4
6 – Augrabies National Park (ANP)	1	0.9

Thomisidae: Thomisids are mainly plant-dwellers, are easily dispersed by wind, and most species have a wide distribution. No species have previously been reported from the ANP. Seven of the eight species have a wide distribution throughout Africa, and only one species is a Northern Cape endemic, *Xysticus namaquensis* Simon, 1910.

Species endemism and conservation: Of the 109 species known from the ANP, most of the species (85%) have a wide distribution and their conservation status is Least Concern (Table 2; Appendix 1). Eight species are data deficient and need more collecting and description of opposite sex.

Eight species, all restricted to the Northern Cape, are of special concern (Table 3). Except for the lesser baboon spider, *Harpactirella lapidaria* Purcell, 1908, which is listed as Rare, seven other species are data deficient. Of these, only the six-eyed sand spider *Hexophthalma leroyi* Lotz, 2018 is endemic to the ANP. Seven species are introduced and most of them have a worldwide distribution (World Spider Catalog 2020).

CONCLUSION

This survey produced the first species list for a national park in the Northern Cape. Eight species have been listed as special concern, of which seven species require more specimens to be sampled to determine their distribution range and to sample the opposite sex. However, given the lack of local human resources to sample in the ANP, and the efforts and costs required for outside resources to sample there, executing a more complete inventory is unlikely to occur soon. Given the urgency for biodiversity data, especially for spider diversity, and distribution data needed for red data assessment, this dataset nonetheless has considerable relevance.

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TABLE 3: Species of special concern endemic protected in the Augrabies National Park (DD = data deficient, known from both sexes; DDT = data deficient; LC = Least Concern).

CLUBIONIDAE		
<i>Clubiona nollothensis</i> Simon, 1910	DDT	Male unknown; only restricted distribution (3 loc.); not revised.
GNAPHOSIDAE		
<i>Nomisia notia</i> Dalmas, 1921	DDT	Male unknown; restricted distribution (3 loc.); not revised.
PHILODROMIDAE		
<i>Thanatus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910	DDT	Male unknown; restricted distribution (3 loc.); not revised
PHYXELIDIDAE		
<i>Namaquarachne thau-matula</i> Griswold, 1990	DD	Both sexes; restricted distribution (3 loc.); revised Griswold (1990)
SICARIIDAE		
<i>Hexophthalma leroyi</i> Lotz, 2018	DDT	Female unknown; only type locality; revised Lotz (2018)
SPARASSIDAE		
<i>Parapalystes euphorbiae</i> Croeser, 1996 (Fig. 3j)	LC	Both sexes; partly revised Croeser (1996).
THERAPHOSIDAE		
<i>Harpactirella lapidaria</i> Purcell, 1908	RA-RE	Both sexes; restricted distribution (3 loc.); not revised
THOMISIDAE		
<i>Xysticus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910 (Fig. 3k)	DDT	Male unknown; restricted distribution (3 loc.); not revised

REFERENCES

CROESER, P.M.C. 1996. A revision of the African huntsman spider genus *Palystes* L. Koch 1875 (Araneae: Heteropodidae). *Annals of the Natal Museum* 37: 1–122.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H., LYLE, R., LOTZ, L.N., HELBERG, L., MATHEBULA, S., VAN DEN BERG, A., MARAIS, P., VAN DEN BERG, A.M., VAN NIEKERK, E. & JOCQUE, R. 2010. *First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)*. ARC – Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria, 1158 pp.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H., LYLE, R., LOTZ, L.N. & MARAIS, P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245–277.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., LYLE, R., LOTZ, L.N., FOORD, S.H. & JOCQUÉ, R. 2018. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve in the Northern Cape province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 60: a1486.

GRISWOLD, C.E. 1990. A revision and phylogenetic analysis of the spider subfamily Phyxelidinae (Araneae, Amaurobiidae). *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History* 196: 1–206.

HADDAD, C.R. 2015. A revision of the southern African two-eyed spider genus *Diploglena* (Araneae: Caponiidae). *African Invertebrates* 56: 343–363.

HADDAD, C.R., LOUW, S.V.D.M. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2004. Spiders (Araneae) in ground covers of pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 10: 97–107.

HADDAD, C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2005. Epigeic spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in Nama Karoo grassland in the Northern Cape Province. *Navorsinge van die Bloemfonteinse Museum* 21: 1–10.

HADDAD, C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2006. Epigeic spiders (Araneae) in pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 12: 12–22.

HADDAD, C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & PEKAR, S. 2005. Arboreal spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 11: 32–41.

HADDAD, C.R. & MARUSIK, Y.M. 2019. Clarifying the taxonomic status and distributions of the spider species collected during the Leonhard Schultze expeditions in western and central southern Africa. *Zootaxa* 4608: 451–483.

LOTZ, L.N. 2018. An update on the spider genus *Hexophthalma* (Araneae: Sicariidae) in the Afrotropical region, with descriptions of new species. *European Journal of Taxonomy* 424: 1–18.

MCGEOCH, M.A., SITHOLE, H., SAMWAYS, M.J., SIMAIKA, J.P., PRYKE, J.S., PICKER, M., UYS, C., ARMSTRONG, A.J., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., ENGELBRECHT, I.A., BRASCHLER, B. & HAMER, M. 2011. Conservation and monitoring of invertebrates in terrestrial protected areas. *Koedoe* 53(#1000): 1–7.

PURCELL, W.F. 1908. Araneae (I). In: Schultze, L. (Ed.), Zoologische und anthropologische Ergebnisse einer Forschungsreise im westlichen und zentralen Südafrika. Erster Band: Systematik und Tiergeographie. Zweite Lieferung. *Denkschriften der Medizinisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Gesellschaft zu Jena*, 13, pp. 203–246.

SIMON, E. 1910. Arachnoidea. Araneae (II). In: Schultze (L.). Zoologische und anthropologische Ergebnisse einer Forschungsreise im westlichen und zentralen Südafrika. *Denkschriften der medizinisch-naturwissenschaftlichen Gesellschaft zu Jena* 16, 175–218.

WORLD SPIDER CATALOG 2020. World Spider Catalog, version 19.5. Natural History Museum Bern. Online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch> [accessed May 2020].

FIGURE 3. Some spiders of the Augrabies National Park: (A) *Uroctea quinquenotata* Simon, 1910 (Oecobiidae); (B) *Ammoxenus coccineus* Simon, 1893 (Ammoxenidae); (C) *Hirriusa arenacea* (Lawrence, 1927) (Philodromidae); (D) *Seothyra fasciata* Purcell, 1904 (Eresidae); (E) *Seothyra* retreat in sand (Eresidae); (F) *Stegodyphus dumicola* Pocock, 1898 (Eresidae); (G) *Diaphorocellus biplagiatus* Simon, 1893 (Palpimanidae); (H) *Hexophthalma leroyi* Lotz, 2018 (Sicariidae); (I) *Loxosceles spinulosa* Purcell, 1904 (Sicariidae); (J) *Parapalystes euphorbiae* Croeser, 1996 (Sparassidae); (K) *Capheris crassimana* (Simon, 1887) (Zodariidae); (L) *Xysticus namaquensis* Simon, 1910 (Thomisidae).
Photos: P. Webb.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of the Augrabies National Park, listing their endemism, conservation status and global distribution). * indicates species previously recorded from the park.

SPECIES	END	CS	DISTR
FAMILY AGELENIDAE			
<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE
<i>Mistaria zuluana</i> (Roer, 1955)*	1	LC	AE
FAMILY AMMOXENIDAE			
<i>Ammoxenus coccineus</i> Simon, 1893	2	LC	STHE
<i>Ammoxenus</i> sp. (new)		NE	
FAMILY ARANEIDAE			
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1885)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)*	1	LC	AE
FAMILY CAPONIIDAE			
<i>Diploglena arida</i> Haddad, 2015*	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY CHEIRACANTHIIDAE			
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
<i>Cheiramiona ferrumfontis</i> Lotz, 2002	4	LC	SAE
FAMILY CLUBIONIDAE			
<i>Clubiona nollothensis</i> Simon, 1910	5	DDT	SAE
FAMILY DICTYNIDAE			
<i>Dictyna</i> sp. undetermined		NE	
FAMILY ERESIDAE			
<i>Gandanameno fumosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Seothyra fasciata</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
<i>Seothyra schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
<i>Stegodyphus bicolor</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1869)*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898*	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY GNAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Asemesthes lineatus</i> Purcell, 1908	1	LC	AE
<i>Asemesthes numisma</i> Tucker, 1923*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Austrodomus scaber</i> (Purcell, 1904)*	3	LC	SAE
<i>Drassodes helenae</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Ibala bilinearis</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Leptodrassus</i> sp. new		NE	

APPENDIX 1: - continued.

SPECIES	END	CS	DISTR
<i>Leptodrassus</i> sp. new		NE	
<i>Prodidomus purpurascens</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
<i>Setaphis</i> sp. new		NE	
<i>Theuma maculata</i> Purcell, 1907*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Xerophaeus hottentottus</i> Purcell, 1908*	3	LC	SAE
<i>Xerophaeus spoliator</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Xerophaeus vickermani</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Zelotes albanicus</i> (Hewitt, 1915)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923*	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY HERSILIIDAE			
<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE
<i>Tyrotama arida</i> (Smithers, 1945)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY LYCOSIDAE			
<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Pardosa injucunda</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	1	LC	AE
<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)*	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY OECOBIIDAE			
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859*	0	LC	C
<i>Uroctea quinquenotata</i> Simon, 1910*	4	LC	SAE
FAMILY OXYOPIIDAE			
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Peucetia crucifera</i> Lawrence, 1927*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
<i>Peucetia viridis</i> (Blackwall, 1858)*	1	LC	AE
FAMILY PALPIMANIDAE			
<i>Diaphorocellus biplagiatus</i> Simon, 1893	2	LC	STHE
<i>Palpimanus giltayi</i> Lessert, 1936*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Palpimanus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY PHILODROMIDAE			
<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
<i>Thanatus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910	5	DDT	SAE
<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
FAMILY PHOLCIDAE			
<i>Artema atlanta</i> Walckenaer, 1837*	0	LC	C
<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i> Huber, 2012	3	LC	SAE
FAMILY PHYXELIDIDAE			
<i>Namaquarachne thaumatula</i> Griswold, 1990	5	DD	NCE

APPENDIX 1: - continued.

SPECIES	END	CS	DISTR
FAMILY SALTICIDAE			
<i>Aelurillus cristatopalpus</i> Simon, 1902	4	DD	SAE
<i>Dendryphantès schultzei</i> Simon, 1910	2	DD	STHE
<i>Euophrys leipoldti</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	4	LC	SAE
<i>Evarcha</i> sp. new		NE	
<i>Hasarius adansonii</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
<i>Heliophanus charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE
<i>Heliophanus patellaris</i> Simon, 1901	2	LC	STHE
<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
<i>Icius insolitus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE
<i>Mexcala rufa</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	2	LC	STHE
<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstacker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyenula</i> sp. new		NE	
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
FAMILY SCYTODIDAE			
<i>Scytodes arenacea</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY SEGESTRIIDAE			
<i>Ariadna karrooica</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
FAMILY SELENOPIDAE			
<i>Anyphops broomi</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Anyphops hessei</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Anyphops namaquensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	4	LC	SAE
FAMILY SICARIIDAE			
<i>Hexophthalma leroyi</i> Lotz, 2018	6	DDT	NCE
<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904*	4	LC	SAE
FAMILY SPARASSIDAE			
<i>Arandisa deserticola</i> Lawrence, 1938*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928*	1	LC	AE
<i>Olios sherwoodi</i> Lessert, 1929*	1	LC	SAE
<i>Parapalystes euphorbiae</i> Croeser, 1996	5	LC	NCE
FAMILY THERAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Harpactira namaquensis</i> Purcell, 1902*	4	LC	SAE
<i>Harpactirella lapidaria</i> Purcell, 1908	5	RARE	NCE
FAMILY THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE

APPENDIX 1: - continued.

SPECIES	END	CS	DISTR
<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
<i>Histagonia deserticola</i> Simon, 1895*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841*	0	LC	C
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Theridion</i> sp. new		NE	
FAMILY THOMISIDAE			
<i>Heriaeus crassispinus</i> Lawrence, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1911	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus machadoi</i> Comellini, 1959	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910	5	DDT	NCE
FAMILY TRACHELIDAE			
<i>Trachelas pusillus</i> Lessert, 1923	1	LC	AE
FAMILY ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846*	0	LC	C
FAMILY ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Caesetius flavoplagiatus</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
<i>Capheris crassimana</i> (Simon, 1887)*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Capheris fitzsimonsi</i> Lawrence, 1936*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Diores triangulifer</i> Simon, 1910*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Psammoduon deserticola</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE

Endemicity (END): (6) only known from the type locality, Au-grabies National Park endemic; (5) endemic to Northern Province; (4) known from two adjoining provinces; (3) endemic to South Africa; (2) endemic to southern Africa; (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region; (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status (CS): LC, least concern; DD, data deficient; NE, not evaluated; VU, vulnerable.

Distribution (DIS): C, cosmopolitan or wider than Africa; AE, African endemic; STHE, southern African endemic; SAE, South African endemic; NCE, Northern Cape endemic.

MORE ON THE SMALLEST CRAB SPIDERS IN AFRICA (ARANEAE: THOMISIDAE: PARABOMIS)

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Abstract

The frog spiders of the genus *Parabomis* are the smallest crab spiders known from Africa. In this paper we report on the colour of live specimens of three species, *P. martini*, *P. pilosus* and *P. megae*. Notes are provided on the general behaviour of *P. megae* from Zimbabwe.

Keywords: Africa, plant-dwellers, Bominæ

INTRODUCTION

In a recent publication by Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2020), the crab spiders of the genus *Parabomis* Kulczyński, 1901 from Africa were revised for the first time. They are very small, only 3 mm in body length, and are the smallest crab spiders known (Fig. 1). With their round bodies, they resemble a seed pot.

Parabomis shares with the other Bominæ the globular body shape, small size and very short legs without spines. They share with *Thomisops* and *Holopelus* the peg-like setae on the promargins of the chelicerae. They can be distinguished by their high carapace, the very broad sloping clypeus, as well as the eyes that are grouped far apart (Fig. 2). *Parabomis* male palps have both a ventral apophysis and a strongly developed retrolateral apophysis on the tibia.

Six *Parabomis* species are presently known from Africa:

- *P. elsae* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020 (South Africa)
- *P. levanderi* Kulczyński, 1901 (Eritrea)
- *P. martini* Lessert, 1919 (Tanzania and rest of Africa)
- *P. megae* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020 (Zimbabwe)
- *P. pilosus* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020 (Botswana)
- *P. wandae* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020 (Ghana)

In this paper we report on the colour of live specimens, with notes on their general behaviour. All specimens housed in collections are alcohol-preserved material, and only on receiving photographs of living specimens did we realize that they lose their colour in alcohol. The second author observed and photographed females and a male *Parabomis* from Zimbabwe. He was also able to capture some of their interesting behavior on camera.

METHODS

As part of the SANSa Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012) photographs were obtained of live specimens. It became clear that the live specimens differ in colour from specimens preserved in alcohol. Images of three species, *P. martini*, *P. pilosus* and *P. megae* became available for comparison.

The second author observed and photographed several individuals of *P. megae* in a garden in Zimbabwe. He was able to capture some of their interesting behaviour on video, shared online at <https://youtu.be/ArCrB0tE1PY>. These are the first observations of their behaviour.

RESULTS

All members of *Parabomis* are small spiders (males 1.9 mm, females 3 mm). In Fig. 1 their size is compared to the tip of a match. In adult females, the extended abdomen can almost resemble a round seed pot (Figs 2 & 3). When they rest on the vegetation they resemble small frogs with the shape of the carapace and abdomen, and the short legs that fold around the body.

FIGURES 1–4. *Parabomis* sp. (1) Indicating the small size; (2–3) Female with extended abdomen; (4) Live specimen resemble a frog.

Due to their small size they are not easily seen. According to label data of specimens in collections, they have been mainly collected beating trees and sweeping grass and herbs in the Grassland (Haddad *et al.* 2013), Savanna (Foord *et al.* 2011) and Thicket Biomes. They have been collected from a variety of habitats ranging from thorny bushveld to the undergrowth of coastal dune forest.

At Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve they have been sampled from yellow flowering *Vachellia* trees, as well as from grasses during the same survey period. From label data, species have been collected from trees such as *Buddleja saligna*, *Euclea crispa*, *Dombeya rotundifolia*, *Vitex rehmannia*, *Vachellia* spp. and *Pterocelastrus tricuspidatus* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2009; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord 2020). In Namibia, specimens were collected from the tree *Grewia monticola*, and according to Lawrence (1928) the spider closely resembles its flowers.

Colour: It has become clear that the museum specimens used in the revision of *Parabomis* lost their colour in alcohol. From the photographs of living specimens it became clear that they are more colourful when alive. The colour of three species based on life specimens is discussed here.

***Parabomis martini*:** This species has been collected from a variety of habitats in the Grassland and Savanna Biomes, ranging from grass, trees in thorny bushveld, and the undergrowth of coastal dune forest. It is widespread in Africa and has been recorded from Tanzania, Kenya, Namibia, Guinea, Malawi, Rwanda, South Africa, Zambia and Zimbabwe. In alcohol the female's carapace is fawn, with the clypeus and eye region strongly infused with white in females (Fig. 5) and darker brown in males (Fig. 7). In a live female photographed at Thyspunt in the Eastern Cape the clypeus and eye area was infused with green and the abdomen had distinct patches of green (Fig. 6). In the male (Fig. 8) the carapace is dark and the abdomen reddish-brown.

FIGURES 5–8 *Parabomis martini*. (5) Colour of alcohol preserved female; (6) Live female from Thyspunt, showing the body infused with green; (7) Colour of alcohol-preserved male; (8) Live male from Thyspunt. Photo credits of live spiders: L. Wiese.

***Parabomis pilosus*:** This species can be recognized by the carapace and abdomen bearing rows of flat-lying translucent club-shaped setae that are longer and denser than in other species, especially on the carapace declivity. The colour of this species do not differ that much from the preserved specimens although the club-shaped setae are less distinct in alcohol material (Fig. 9). They have been sampled from the Okavango Delta in Botswana as well as in the northern parts of the Limpopo Province in South Africa. Specimens were sampled by sweeping grass and herbs. In Tshipise, a female was sampled from a silk retreat made between leaves (Figs 10–12). Adults were sampled in November and December.

FIGURES 9–12. *Parabomis pilosus*. (9) Colour of alcohol preserved female; (10–12) Live female from Tshipise, showing the body infused with brown. Photo credits of live spiders: J. Wilkinson.

***Parabomis megae*:** These small spiders are commonly found in Zimbabwe. A single male specimen was also now identified from the Kruger National Park, South Africa. In alcohol, the female carapace is fawn, with the eye region infused with white (Fig. 13), and in the male dark brown (Fig. 15). In live specimens, the immature female is whitish but becomes more colourful after she has moulted (Fig. 14). In live male specimens the carapace is almost black (Fig. 16).

FIGURES 13–16. *Parabomis megae*. (13) Colour of alcohol-preserved female; (14) Live female from Zimbabwe; (15) Colour of alcohol-preserved male; (16) Live male. Photo credits of live spiders: Jonathan Whitaker.

FIELD OBSERVATIONS IN ZIMBABWE

FIGURES 17–20. *Parabomis megae*. (17) Female on plant in garden in Harare; (18) Male sampled from garden; (19) Palp of male sampled in garden; (20) Male palp from Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2020). Photo credits of live spiders: J. Whitaker.

Identification: The second author observed the small spider walking around on a plant in a garden in Harare, Zimbabwe on October 2020 (Fig. 17) for the first time. It was identified as a *Parabomis* sp., but it was only after a male was collected (Fig. 18) that we were able to identify it as *P. megae*, a species recently described from Zimbabwe (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord 2020). Females are more difficult to identify and it is mainly the shape of the retrolateral apophysis in the male that helps with identification (Figs 19-20). In *P. megae*, the retrolateral apophysis curves upwards.

Male: The live male has a very dark, almost black carapace, with some of the leg segments dark. It differs from the alcohol-preserved brown males (Fig. 15). In live specimens the carapace, chelicerae, palp and femora are black. The abdomen is white and the dorsal part is covered by a shield-like patch with a mottled reddish-brown colour. These images enabled us to identify a male photographed in the Kruger National Park by Ronelle as *P. megae* (Figs 23-24). *Parabomis megae* was previously only known from Zimbabwe.

Immature and female: The first spider observed was white with only a few black spots (Fig. 25). Only after the final moult (Fig. 26) did the first colour appear on the abdomen (Figs 27-28). The abdomen is still flat, forming crevices and humps in the young female.

On 14 January 2020 a female was seen with extended abdomen, possibly ready to lay eggs. The abdomen was largely extended, round, with a pinkish tint around the anterior abdominal border. The clypeus had a faint greenish hue (Figs 29-30; 33-34).

FIGURES 21–24. *Parabomis megae*. 21-22. Male from garden in Harare; 23-24. Male photographed in the Kruger National Park. Photos: 21-22 J. Whitaker. 23-24 Ronelle.

FIGURES 25–28. *Parabomis megae*. (25) Immature female; (26) Female after moult; (27-28) Female. Photos: J. Whitaker.

FIGURES 29–30. *Parabomis megae*, adult female. Photos: J. Whitaker.

Behaviour: One female was observed over a 24-hour period, beginning mid-afternoon. She was active throughout the afternoon, remaining stationary overnight and for most of the morning (Figs 31-34). Other individuals were observed out on a strand of silk at night, but this one simply sat under a leaf. With their round bodies and short legs, they are clumsy and she frequently lost her footing, dropping down on a silk thread only to climb back up again. Movement between branches was accomplished by letting out silk into the wind and then using it to bridge gaps of up to 1.5m. The legs are so short that they struggle to directly pull out the silk, instead first dropping down on a line (sometimes repeatedly) to initiate a strand, which could then be taken out further by the wind.

This activity can be viewed at <https://youtu.be/ArCrB0tE1PY> Unfortunately due to their small size, they are easily lost in vegetation.

Parabomis strike range is quite limited. They sit by the best flowers (Fig. 35) and catch prey that landed right in front of them (Fig. 36). They seem to be quite successful and feed on a variety of insects visiting the flowers (Figs 37, 38). The males feed while on the plant (Fig. 38) or they hang from a thread (Figs 39, 40) while feeding. This was also seen being done by *Mystaria* species (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015).

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2015. Interesting feeding behaviour. *SANSa NEWS* 23: 11.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & FOORD, S.H. 2020. Revision of the Afrotropical crab-spider genus *Parabomis* Kulczyński, 1901 (Araneae: Thomisidae). *Zootaxa* 4899: 161–174.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., VAN DEN BERG, A. & PRENDINI, L. 2009. A checklist of spiders and scorpions of the Nylsvley Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50(1): 1–9.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., LYLE, R. & VAN DEN BERG, A.M. 2012. Bioinformatics on the spiders of South Africa. *Serket* 13: 121–127.
- FOORD, S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & HADDAD, C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- HADDAD, C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., FOORD, S.H., LOTZ, L.N. & LYLE, R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 97–122.
- LAWRENCE, R.F. 1928. Contributions to a knowledge of the fauna of South-West Africa. vii. Arachnida (Part 2). *Annals of the South African Museum* 25: 217–312.

FIGURES 31–34. *Parabomis megae*. (31-32) Young female moving around on leaf; (33-34) Adult female possibly searching for leaf to make a retreat to deposit the eggs. Photos: J. Whitaker.

FIGURES 35–40. *Parabomis megae*. (35-37) Female catching prey; (38-40) Adult male feeding Photos: J. Whitaker.